

Appendix A: Absorption line profiles and fit results

Individual absorption systems are displayed in Figures [A.1](#) to [A.8](#). The corresponding best-fit parameters are listed in Table [A.1](#).

Fig. A.1: Continued

Fig. A.2: Same as Fig. A.1 but for system 1527 b.

Fig. A.1: C IV $\lambda\lambda 1548, 1550$ absorption in system 1527 a. The normalized flux is shown in green and the corresponding 1σ error in light-blue. A double Gaussian fit is shown in red (§ 3.2). Each panel corresponds to a binned arc spectrum having arbitrary spaxel coordinates (cf. Fig. 1) indicated to the left side. *Figure continuing in the next column.*

Fig. A.3: Same as Fig. A.1 but for system 1527 c.

Fig. A.4: Same as Fig. A.1 but for system G311 a. *Figure continuing in the next three columns.*

Fig. A.4: Continued

Fig. A.4: Continued

Fig. A.4: Continued

Fig. A.5: Same as Fig. A.1 but for system 0033 a.

Fig. A.6: Same as Fig. A.1 but for system 0033 b. *Figure continuing in the next column.*

Fig. A.7: Same as Fig. A.1 but for system 2111 a.

Fig. A.8: Same as Fig. A.1 but for system 2111 b. *Figure continuing in the next column.*

Table A.1: Gaussian fits results

Spaxel Coord. j, i	v [km/s]	σ_{obs} [km/s]	W_0 [Å]
1527 a $z = 2.0552$			
12,10	-61.7 ± 28.2	168.0 ± 20.2	1.42 ± 0.28
12,11	24.7 ± 13.9	143.2 ± 10.5	1.73 ± 0.2
12,12	7.8 ± 24.0	164.0 ± 17.3	1.74 ± 0.3
12,13	23.5 ± 15.6	145.9 ± 11.9	1.89 ± 0.24
12,14	31.9 ± 13.8	150.8 ± 10.0	1.79 ± 0.2
12,15	-28.8 ± 14.6	148.9 ± 11.1	1.79 ± 0.2
12,16	-32.4 ± 18.0	160.2 ± 13.2	1.83 ± 0.23
12,17	-38.9 ± 28.0	183.9 ± 20.2	1.79 ± 0.31
13,10	-63.6 ± 15.2	99.0 ± 14.6	1.28 ± 0.28
13,11	25.1 ± 13.4	113.8 ± 11.9	1.35 ± 0.21
13,12	118.7 ± 26.1	157.5 ± 18.9	1.33 ± 0.26
13,13	15.7 ± 13.9	139.2 ± 10.8	1.52 ± 0.18
13,14	-0.4 ± 9.5	147.3 ± 7.0	1.72 ± 0.13
13,15	-10.7 ± 8.7	151.8 ± 6.5	1.96 ± 0.13
13,16	-20.6 ± 9.6	147.5 ± 7.6	1.91 ± 0.14
13,17	10.0 ± 7.5	150.5 ± 5.7	1.85 ± 0.1
13,18	5.0 ± 7.2	146.7 ± 5.4	1.59 ± 0.09
13,19	10.2 ± 12.6	153.5 ± 9.4	1.89 ± 0.18
13,20	67.3 ± 29.1	170.5 ± 20.8	2.2 ± 0.43
14,11	-0.3 ± 24.3	126.5 ± 20.0	1.63 ± 0.41
14,12	-53.2 ± 25.2	113.3 ± 22.7	1.46 ± 0.41
14,14	-0.5 ± 17.6	112.5 ± 15.6	1.45 ± 0.32
14,15	-62.6 ± 18.6	144.6 ± 14.0	1.87 ± 0.29
14,16	42.8 ± 13.2	104.9 ± 12.4	1.15 ± 0.2
14,17	27.7 ± 9.8	129.2 ± 7.8	1.41 ± 0.14
14,18	0.5 ± 7.7	158.9 ± 5.7	1.85 ± 0.1
14,19	-45.4 ± 10.1	172.9 ± 7.6	2.08 ± 0.13
14,20	-20.8 ± 20.1	172.9 ± 14.8	1.72 ± 0.22
14,21	-23.5 ± 28.6	149.4 ± 21.3	1.82 ± 0.42
15,19	73.2 ± 24.3	161.3 ± 17.8	1.31 ± 0.24
15,20	-33.5 ± 13.2	143.5 ± 10.5	1.83 ± 0.19
15,21	-21.7 ± 18.5	121.6 ± 15.9	1.57 ± 0.29
1527 b $z = 2.1626$			
12,10	-14.2 ± 20.2	148.0 ± 15.1	1.27 ± 0.22
12,11	-103.4 ± 28.3	186.8 ± 20.3	1.29 ± 0.23
12,12	26.6 ± 21.2	152.7 ± 16.2	1.58 ± 0.25
12,13	45.6 ± 19.7	129.2 ± 16.7	1.32 ± 0.25
13,13	124.0 ± 13.1	106.8 ± 12.0	0.91 ± 0.15
13,14	15.5 ± 24.1	179.0 ± 16.9	0.87 ± 0.13
13,15	-115.9 ± 23.0	177.4 ± 16.7	0.9 ± 0.14
13,17	-0.4 ± 12.2	140.2 ± 9.4	0.77 ± 0.09
13,19	89.3 ± 12.8	98.7 ± 12.2	0.67 ± 0.12
14,13	23.4 ± 34.5	150.3 ± 26.3	1.41 ± 0.37
14,16	86.4 ± 16.8	65.1 ± 16.9	0.43 ± 0.17
14,18	90.8 ± 13.7	153.7 ± 9.9	0.74 ± 0.08
15,20	32.7 ± 31.5	151.6 ± 23.2	0.65 ± 0.17
16,20	-39.8 ± 29.9	157.4 ± 21.9	1.71 ± 0.39
1527 c $z = 2.5430$			
11,10	-46.4 ± 16.8	82.3 ± 17.0	1.06 ± 0.33
12,13	28.0 ± 24.7	147.5 ± 18.4	0.84 ± 0.17
12,14	17.6 ± 17.4	85.4 ± 17.4	0.4 ± 0.12
12,15	-8.3 ± 14.5	60.9 ± 14.9	0.24 ± 0.09
12,16	-46.4 ± 11.7	58.1 ± 11.2	0.33 ± 0.1
13,10	-2.2 ± 15.3	58.1 ± 15.8	0.46 ± 0.18
13,11	35.3 ± 23.0	117.9 ± 20.2	0.71 ± 0.17
13,13	-16.3 ± 10.4	90.5 ± 10.2	0.79 ± 0.12
13,14	23.8 ± 7.4	72.1 ± 7.4	0.52 ± 0.07
13,16	-4.1 ± 8.5	73.3 ± 8.6	0.43 ± 0.07
13,17	8.2 ± 6.0	79.3 ± 6.0	0.54 ± 0.06
13,18	-5.8 ± 6.6	98.1 ± 6.3	0.56 ± 0.05
13,19	-53.6 ± 14.8	100.9 ± 14.0	0.51 ± 0.11
14,16	19.2 ± 13.0	64.7 ± 12.8	0.38 ± 0.11

Spaxel Coord. (j, i)	v (km/s)	σ_{obs} (km/s)	W_0 (Å)	Spaxel Coord. (j, i)	v (km/s)	σ_{obs} (km/s)	W_0 (Å)
14,17	-12.9 ± 9.5	85.6 ± 9.3	0.54 ± 0.08	60,17	28.5 ± 7.8	99.0 ± 7.5	0.69 ± 0.08
14,18	16.0 ± 5.9	101.2 ± 5.6	0.69 ± 0.05	60,18	-8.9 ± 11.2	104.4 ± 10.3	0.65 ± 0.1
14,19	-3.0 ± 6.1	81.2 ± 6.0	0.53 ± 0.06	60,19	-24.5 ± 20.0	107.0 ± 18.6	0.68 ± 0.19
14,20	-9.0 ± 12.3	101.6 ± 11.6	0.6 ± 0.11	60,20	-29.5 ± 17.7	66.1 ± 18.1	0.53 ± 0.21
15,17	10.7 ± 17.6	102.3 ± 16.7	0.71 ± 0.16	61,8	-59.2 ± 33.7	127.6 ± 27.4	1.25 ± 0.44
15,18	2.8 ± 16.7	90.0 ± 16.5	0.55 ± 0.15	61,10	-68.8 ± 23.8	89.1 ± 23.5	0.55 ± 0.21
15,19	18.2 ± 12.4	82.6 ± 12.3	0.53 ± 0.12	61,11	38.0 ± 10.4	64.6 ± 10.6	0.49 ± 0.12
15,20	42.7 ± 8.9	74.2 ± 9.1	0.63 ± 0.11	61,12	18.0 ± 13.3	70.0 ± 13.4	0.34 ± 0.09
16,19	29.7 ± 33.7	133.0 ± 27.9	1.38 ± 0.42	61,13	-2.0 ± 13.5	119.4 ± 11.4	0.7 ± 0.1
G311 a $z = 2.1894$				61,14	-13.3 ± 10.8	112.9 ± 9.8	0.84 ± 0.1
12,54	19.9 ± 11.2	64.6 ± 11.9	0.42 ± 0.1	61,15	1.3 ± 7.5	91.2 ± 7.5	0.65 ± 0.07
13,53	-24.7 ± 17.8	64.6 ± 18.3	0.57 ± 0.24	61,16	-5.8 ± 7.0	82.2 ± 7.0	0.6 ± 0.07
34,47	2.4 ± 18.7	109.8 ± 17.6	0.53 ± 0.12	62,8	53.8 ± 20.3	85.3 ± 20.4	0.43 ± 0.15
34,48	-29.2 ± 10.0	98.2 ± 9.6	0.5 ± 0.07	62,9	0.1 ± 12.5	111.9 ± 11.1	0.48 ± 0.07
35,47	6.3 ± 8.7	79.3 ± 9.0	0.5 ± 0.08	62,10	69.0 ± 28.3	167.2 ± 22.2	0.83 ± 0.16
35,48	38.3 ± 11.9	133.6 ± 9.6	0.74 ± 0.08	62,11	0.6 ± 16.4	114.5 ± 14.5	0.52 ± 0.1
36,46	12.8 ± 14.6	104.1 ± 13.7	0.8 ± 0.15	62,12	29.1 ± 9.7	93.8 ± 9.6	0.64 ± 0.09
36,47	23.2 ± 11.4	81.4 ± 11.6	0.44 ± 0.09	62,13	-3.0 ± 15.4	120.4 ± 13.4	0.83 ± 0.13
39,44	-14.4 ± 14.8	92.2 ± 15.0	0.62 ± 0.14	62,14	-17.7 ± 15.2	94.6 ± 14.7	0.82 ± 0.18
40,43	15.8 ± 9.2	75.7 ± 9.3	0.51 ± 0.09	63,9	-11.2 ± 21.7	108.8 ± 19.6	0.53 ± 0.14
40,44	2.8 ± 9.4	88.1 ± 9.6	0.49 ± 0.07	63,10	-20.5 ± 12.4	91.5 ± 12.1	0.98 ± 0.19
40,45	21.5 ± 18.5	108.3 ± 16.8	0.46 ± 0.11	63,11	43.4 ± 11.3	64.6 ± 11.9	0.83 ± 0.2
41,43	5.6 ± 7.9	86.0 ± 8.0	0.59 ± 0.07	63,12	-2.8 ± 15.7	64.6 ± 15.5	0.68 ± 0.24
41,44	51.0 ± 18.0	113.9 ± 16.3	0.74 ± 0.15	0033 a $z = 2.2813$			
42,41	75.0 ± 17.9	110.3 ± 16.0	0.73 ± 0.17	23,10	-60.0 ± 28.6	153.7 ± 22.1	1.82 ± 0.39
42,42	-0.8 ± 12.1	64.6 ± 11.6	0.37 ± 0.09	24,9	255.7 ± 21.1	93.9 ± 20.6	0.74 ± 0.24
42,43	18.0 ± 15.1	83.4 ± 15.5	0.42 ± 0.11	24,10	21.5 ± 14.0	140.4 ± 11.6	1.35 ± 0.16
43,40	-2.8 ± 13.9	64.6 ± 14.0	0.39 ± 0.13	24,11	9.2 ± 16.7	143.6 ± 13.6	1.11 ± 0.15
43,41	-9.9 ± 7.4	93.3 ± 7.2	0.57 ± 0.07	25,8	-105.6 ± 34.3	129.1 ± 27.9	1.45 ± 0.47
43,42	7.0 ± 10.2	90.4 ± 10.1	0.52 ± 0.08	25,9	13.9 ± 20.8	155.2 ± 16.6	1.51 ± 0.23
43,43	-45.6 ± 26.7	101.5 ± 25.3	0.66 ± 0.24	25,10	-17.3 ± 11.2	158.5 ± 9.0	1.33 ± 0.11
44,39	-34.4 ± 14.3	65.1 ± 14.7	0.64 ± 0.21	25,11	26.6 ± 11.2	153.4 ± 9.0	1.3 ± 0.11
44,40	-8.1 ± 9.3	82.2 ± 9.3	0.37 ± 0.06	26,9	-23.8 ± 19.0	137.6 ± 15.6	1.09 ± 0.18
44,41	-8.2 ± 6.9	80.9 ± 7.0	0.52 ± 0.06	26,10	-1.8 ± 17.7	192.6 ± 14.3	1.39 ± 0.14
45,39	-43.5 ± 18.8	72.6 ± 19.1	0.45 ± 0.18	26,11	71.9 ± 20.1	154.4 ± 15.8	1.36 ± 0.19
45,40	-28.6 ± 20.9	103.6 ± 19.6	0.43 ± 0.12	27,8	-22.7 ± 26.4	145.4 ± 22.1	1.88 ± 0.4
45,41	30.1 ± 33.1	126.1 ± 27.1	0.62 ± 0.21	27,9	-10.9 ± 18.6	163.0 ± 14.6	1.54 ± 0.19
46,39	27.8 ± 27.7	124.5 ± 23.3	0.83 ± 0.23	27,10	-24.5 ± 12.9	157.7 ± 10.3	1.42 ± 0.13
46,40	31.0 ± 27.2	98.7 ± 26.1	0.89 ± 0.36	27,11	143.6 ± 14.9	113.0 ± 13.8	1.46 ± 0.25
47,37	5.2 ± 15.2	64.6 ± 14.5	0.62 ± 0.18	28,8	-11.4 ± 23.9	113.3 ± 21.3	1.46 ± 0.4
48,35	19.9 ± 20.7	93.8 ± 20.4	0.8 ± 0.26	28,10	-25.9 ± 21.6	163.2 ± 17.1	1.81 ± 0.27
48,36	29.0 ± 16.0	121.7 ± 13.7	0.65 ± 0.12	29,9	-45.4 ± 31.6	152.7 ± 24.9	1.86 ± 0.44
48,37	4.0 ± 16.0	85.3 ± 15.8	0.47 ± 0.13	29,10	26.1 ± 32.3	143.9 ± 26.1	1.86 ± 0.48
49,35	91.7 ± 21.6	94.3 ± 21.4	0.43 ± 0.15	0033 b $z = 2.3356$			
49,36	29.7 ± 14.3	114.7 ± 12.9	0.77 ± 0.14	23,10	123.2 ± 18.9	97.6 ± 18.0	1.26 ± 0.36
57,22	-35.8 ± 17.4	64.6 ± 17.8	0.64 ± 0.26	23,11	123.0 ± 18.5	105.7 ± 17.3	1.36 ± 0.34
57,23	-58.9 ± 14.6	64.6 ± 14.7	0.31 ± 0.11	24,9	-16.4 ± 19.4	134.1 ± 15.3	1.48 ± 0.26
57,24	-12.8 ± 9.6	70.8 ± 9.6	0.37 ± 0.07	24,10	1.9 ± 12.9	134.6 ± 10.6	1.62 ± 0.18
57,25	-29.9 ± 7.7	72.9 ± 8.0	0.45 ± 0.07	24,11	10.2 ± 8.7	122.0 ± 7.4	1.43 ± 0.13
57,26	14.4 ± 29.3	112.9 ± 25.6	0.59 ± 0.21	25,9	35.4 ± 17.1	120.8 ± 15.1	1.34 ± 0.23
58,20	50.0 ± 30.0	123.2 ± 26.1	1.51 ± 0.45	25,10	12.7 ± 8.3	153.4 ± 6.4	1.69 ± 0.1
58,21	-9.0 ± 20.7	117.0 ± 18.9	0.79 ± 0.18	25,11	-20.7 ± 7.0	130.2 ± 5.9	1.57 ± 0.1
58,22	-27.2 ± 10.4	113.4 ± 9.6	0.87 ± 0.1	25,12	-17.1 ± 30.5	185.3 ± 23.5	2.16 ± 0.39
58,23	-35.7 ± 4.6	73.4 ± 4.9	0.59 ± 0.05	26,9	34.6 ± 13.7	146.7 ± 10.1	1.67 ± 0.18
58,24	-19.7 ± 8.6	74.9 ± 8.8	0.43 ± 0.07	26,10	-0.2 ± 9.9	163.0 ± 7.9	1.75 ± 0.12
58,25	-41.4 ± 11.7	64.6 ± 12.1	0.39 ± 0.1	26,11	-14.3 ± 14.5	103.0 ± 13.6	0.99 ± 0.18
59,16	63.1 ± 11.2	69.5 ± 11.1	0.7 ± 0.15	26,12	-36.7 ± 24.8	115.9 ± 21.2	1.43 ± 0.41
59,17	-5.5 ± 14.4	64.6 ± 14.0	0.36 ± 0.11	27,9	-41.2 ± 16.3	154.9 ± 12.8	1.72 ± 0.2
59,18	-15.8 ± 13.8	64.6 ± 13.2	0.41 ± 0.11	27,10	-30.6 ± 14.8	192.7 ± 11.6	2.02 ± 0.17
59,20	11.2 ± 19.0	69.8 ± 19.1	0.29 ± 0.12	28,9	9.3 ± 21.4	170.9 ± 15.6	2.09 ± 0.28
59,21	-7.0 ± 7.8	77.2 ± 8.0	0.51 ± 0.07	28,10	-115.2 ± 20.3	152.2 ± 16.3	1.97 ± 0.3
59,22	17.5 ± 10.6	83.2 ± 10.9	0.45 ± 0.08	29,10	107.3 ± 30.6	202.1 ± 21.7	2.61 ± 0.45
60,13	94.7 ± 18.9	88.1 ± 18.6	1.14 ± 0.36	2111 a $z = 2.4368$			
60,14	29.0 ± 19.6	130.5 ± 16.5	1.1 ± 0.2	22,13	-17.8 ± 21.6	98.8 ± 20.6	1.28 ± 0.41
60,15	-23.0 ± 7.7	107.7 ± 7.2	0.7 ± 0.07	24,17	156.0 ± 31.3	138.1 ± 24.5	1.05 ± 0.28
60,16	-8.5 ± 6.0	107.0 ± 5.7	0.81 ± 0.06	25,17	35.7 ± 32.0	130.7 ± 26.1	0.57 ± 0.17

Spaxel Coord. (j, i)	v (km/s)	σ_{obs} (km/s)	W_0 (Å)
25,18	-11.9 ± 12.9	112.9 ± 11.5	0.97 ± 0.15
25,19	-59.6 ± 24.4	107.2 ± 22.5	1.04 ± 0.34
26,20	-114.9 ± 17.8	59.9 ± 16.5	0.39 ± 0.16
26,21	-4.0 ± 11.2	59.9 ± 12.2	0.71 ± 0.21
27,20	-7.1 ± 29.8	142.7 ± 22.8	1.12 ± 0.29
27,21	11.6 ± 12.7	95.4 ± 12.5	1.16 ± 0.2
28,23	7.3 ± 24.1	107.7 ± 22.3	1.08 ± 0.35
30,24	113.5 ± 26.3	123.0 ± 22.8	0.52 ± 0.14
30,25	22.7 ± 16.7	67.9 ± 16.8	0.66 ± 0.22
2111 b $z = 2.5370$			
20,7	85.9 ± 20.2	103.0 ± 18.9	1.33 ± 0.37
22,12	0.3 ± 31.1	106.7 ± 28.9	1.38 ± 0.57
23,15	-42.8 ± 27.3	134.0 ± 21.9	1.73 ± 0.43
23,16	25.3 ± 23.3	85.5 ± 23.1	1.1 ± 0.44
24,17	-22.5 ± 10.8	76.2 ± 10.9	0.98 ± 0.21
24,18	-38.7 ± 15.8	115.8 ± 13.7	1.5 ± 0.28
25,17	-19.5 ± 12.8	99.2 ± 12.3	0.72 ± 0.13
25,18	70.0 ± 17.4	147.7 ± 12.8	1.17 ± 0.16
25,19	229.3 ± 34.6	146.1 ± 28.2	1.66 ± 0.46
26,19	14.5 ± 19.7	88.3 ± 19.3	1.14 ± 0.37
26,20	12.0 ± 11.3	68.3 ± 11.2	0.88 ± 0.21
26,21	-32.1 ± 11.0	65.7 ± 11.2	0.85 ± 0.21
27,21	-25.4 ± 11.2	99.9 ± 10.7	1.22 ± 0.19
28,21	1.8 ± 26.0	94.8 ± 24.9	0.93 ± 0.37
28,22	-35.9 ± 17.8	112.1 ± 15.8	1.15 ± 0.25
28,23	6.8 ± 21.1	74.8 ± 21.2	0.68 ± 0.28
29,23	46.2 ± 13.2	73.6 ± 13.3	0.95 ± 0.24
29,24	30.8 ± 19.7	145.6 ± 15.1	1.56 ± 0.26
29,25	11.0 ± 20.6	122.3 ± 17.5	1.58 ± 0.36
30,23	-33.1 ± 26.9	142.8 ± 20.5	1.24 ± 0.29
30,25	-23.0 ± 13.4	88.5 ± 13.3	1.01 ± 0.23
30,26	-37.8 ± 20.8	107.9 ± 18.9	1.39 ± 0.38
31,24	3.9 ± 24.5	124.6 ± 20.0	1.46 ± 0.38
31,25	3.1 ± 16.6	64.8 ± 16.8	0.84 ± 0.31
31,29	-11.2 ± 21.4	101.1 ± 20.3	1.31 ± 0.4